

Istituto Nanoscienze

Technical Report:

YAMBO on ARM architectures

Nicola Spallanzani

S3 Centre, Istituto Nanoscienze, CNR, Modena, Italy

Corresponding author: nicola.spallanzani@nano.cnr.it

Abstract

This technical report presents the successful porting of the YAMBO code to ARM architectures, demonstrating compatibility with both everyday devices, such as Apple MacBooks, and highly parallel HPC systems like Fugaku and Deucalion. Utilizing the GCC compiler suite, this porting effort enables the study of complex materials by performing calculations of their electronic and optical properties on energy-efficient ARM platforms. The ultimate goal is the preparation of the code for deployment on JUPITER, Europe's first exascale supercomputer. The upcoming integration of this porting into the official YAMBO repository will be accompanied by detailed installation instructions in the YAMBO wiki pages, following the next official code release.

Keywords: YAMBO code, ARM architecture, Fugaku, Deucalion, software porting, MaX, HPC.

Contents

Abstract	2
Contents	3
Introduction	4
YAMBO CODE PORTING ON ARM SYSTEMS	4
QUANTUM ESPRESSO	5
BENCHMARK USED TO TEST THE PORTING	5
Porting on MacBook Air	6
ENVIRONMENT	6
COMPILATION OF QUANTUM ESPRESSO v7.4	7
YAMBO branch tech-arm	8
Porting on Fugaku	10
COMPILATION IN INTERACTIVE MODE WITH SPACK	10
YAMBO COMPILATION ON FUGAKU WITH SPACK	11
LAUNCHING THE GrCo GW WORKFLOW VIA BATCH SCRIPTS	12
Porting on Deucalion	14
YAMBO COMPILATION ON DEUCALION IN INTERACTIVE MODE	15
LAUNCHING THE GrCo GW WORKFLOW VIA BATCH SCRIPTS	16
Conclusions	18
Acknowledgment	19
Appendix	20
Benchmark GrCo input files	20

Introduction

Developing the porting of a High-Performance Computing (HPC) application to ARM architecture is of significant importance in the current computational landscape. ARM, originally known for its energy-efficient processors in mobile and embedded devices, has made considerable advances in performance. The shift to ARM offers several advantages, including improved energy efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness, which are crucial factors for large-scale HPC workloads. As demand grows for greener and more powerful computing solutions, ARM's architecture provides a pathway to achieving sustainable and efficient high-performance computing. Porting HPC applications to ARM also enhances the adaptability and longevity of software, enabling it to leverage ARM-based systems like Fugaku¹, one of the world's most powerful supercomputers, and Deucalion², one of the supercomputers of the EuroHPC ecosystem, both systems equipped with Fujitsu A64FX³ chips. In essence, this transition not only aligns with technological advancements but also paves the way for future innovations in HPC. The latest NVIDIA Grace CPU⁴, which is based on ARM technology, further enhances this ecosystem by combining ARM's energy-efficient architecture with NVIDIA's powerful GPU acceleration, like in the new NVIDIA's Grace Hopper Superchip⁵, which will power the JUPITER supercomputer (first exascale system in Europe), enabling unprecedented performance in AI and scientific computing workloads. These advancements make ARM-based systems a competitive choice for high-demand applications, expanding the possibilities for HPC in research and industry.

YAMBO CODE PORTING ON ARM SYSTEMS

YAMBO^{6,7,8} is an open-source code released within the GPL licence implementing first-principles methods based on Green's function theory to describe excited-state properties of realistic materials. These methods include the GW approximation, the Bethe-Salpeter equation (BSE), electron-phonon interaction and non-equilibrium Green's

¹ <https://www.r-ccs.riken.jp/en/fugaku/about/>

² <https://rnca.fccn.pt/en/deucalion/>

³ <https://www.fujitsu.com/global/products/computing/servers/supercomputer/a64fx/>

⁴ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/data-center/grace-cpu/>

⁵ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/data-center/grace-hopper-superchip/>

⁶ <https://www.yambo-code.eu/>

⁷ D. Sangalli et al. 2019 J. Phys.: Condens. Matter 31 325902

⁸ A. Marini et al. 2009 Comput. Phys. Commun. 180, 1392

function theory (NEGF).

Porting the YAMBO code to ARM architecture would grant the possibility to exploit supercomputers such as Fugaku and Deucalion (ARM partition). These are highly parallel systems that would open up opportunities for testing and developing new algorithms to improve YAMBO's parallel efficiency and provide to users the possibility to perform calculations of electronic and optical properties of complex materials.

The ultimate goal is to prepare the code to be ported and installed on JUPITER, the first European exascale supercomputer.

Nonetheless, it is of significant importance also to make YAMBO installable on systems like workstations and laptops that use ARM architecture (such as Apple devices) for energy efficiency reasons. This would allow researchers to test YAMBO even before gaining access to supercomputer resources.

QUANTUM ESPRESSO

From YAMBO webpage: YAMBO relies on previously computed ground-state properties and for this reason it is interfaced with other density functional theory (DFT) codes.

The DFT code chosen for the ground-state calculations used by YAMBO as input files is QUANTUM ESPRESSO^{9,10,11}, another of the lighthouse codes of the MaX CoE.

From QUANTUM ESPRESSO website: QUANTUM ESPRESSO is an integrated suite of Open-Source computer codes for electronic-structure calculations and materials modeling at the nanoscale. It is based on density-functional theory, plane waves, and pseudopotentials.

BENCHMARK USED TO TEST THE PORTING

GrCo GW workflow

For benchmark purposes, we perform calculation of quasi-particle corrections on a graphene/Co interface (GrCo) composed by a graphene sheet adsorbed on a Co slab 4 layer thick, also including a vacuum layer as large as the Co slab. The test represents a

⁹ <https://www.quantum-espresso.org/>

¹⁰ P Giannozzi et al. 2017 J.Phys.:Condens.Matter 29, 465901

¹¹ P Giannozzi et al. 2009 J. Phys. Condens. Matter 21, 395502

prototype calculation, as it involves the evaluation of the response function, of the Hartree-Fock self-energy and, finally, of the correlation part of the self-energy.

The YAMBO test starts from a ground-state calculation (performed with QUANTUM ESPRESSO) using a 6x6x1 k-point grid, resulting in a total of 7 irreducible k-points. The GW workflow applies the Plasmon Pole Approximation (PPA) for the screened interaction, includes 2000 bands and an energy cutoff for the irreducible response function (X_0) of 20 Ry (both production values) in order to make the test meaningful for scalability assessment.

Porting on MacBook Air

Apple's adoption of ARM architecture in its systems¹² further underscores ARM's potential, as it leverages ARM's energy efficiency and processing power to optimize performance across a wide range of devices.

System description:

- MacBook Air
- Chip Apple M1, 8 cores: 4 High (3,20 GHz), 4 Low (2,00 GHz)
- Chip Apple M2, 8 cores: 4 High (3.49 GHz), 4 Low (2.42 GHz)
- Tested on
 - macOS Sonoma v14.3.1 (M2)
 - macOS Sonoma v14.6.1 (M1)
 - macOS Sequoia v15.1 (M1)

ENVIRONMENT

From YAMBO webpage: YAMBO is a Fortran/C code that exploits a number of optimized libraries such as BLAS, LAPACK, FFTW, SCALAPACK, NetCDF/HDF5, PETSC, and SLEPC. The code is parallelized over several MPI+OpenMP levels. YAMBO stores information in several database files (the biggest reaching a few GBs in size for our systems) for which a NetCDF/HDF5 format is adopted, optimizing IO and data portability.

Therefore, in order to install the code, it is necessary to set up a development

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Apple_M1

environment on the target computer. At a minimum, this requires Fortran and C/C++ compilers suitable for compiling code on ARM architectures, such as the GNU Compiler Collection (GCC). HomeBrew, a package manager for macOS (or Linux), was used to install the compilers and some of the libraries needed. For libraries not available in the HomeBrew repository or those that did not meet the necessary requirements, the installation was handled by the automated procedure developed within YAMBO itself.

Also the software HomeBrew needs to be installed first:

```
/bin/bash -c "$(curl -fsSL
https://raw.githubusercontent.com/Homebrew/install/HEAD/install.sh)"
```

And to install the compiler and the libraries is possible to use these commands:

```
brew install gcc
brew install open-mpi
brew install openblas fftw libxc
brew install hdf5 netcdf netcdf-fortran
```

In the first test machine (MacBook Air M1, macOS Sonoma v14.6.1) this is a partial list of the installed packages and versions:

```
% brew list --versions
```

```
[...]
cmake 3.26.4
fftw 3.3.10_1
gcc 14.2.0_1
hdf5 1.14.4.3
libxc 6.2.0
netcdf 4.9.2_2
netcdf-fortran 4.6.1_1
open-mpi 5.0.5
openblas 0.3.28
scalapack 2.2.0_1
gcc-aarch64-embedded 12.2.rel1
```

COMPILATION OF QUANTUM ESPRESSO v7.4

It is possible to have the software form the download page of the webpage after a quick registration.

The configuration was done using the autotool system with the following command:

```
./configure F90=gfortran-14 CC=gcc-14 MPIF90=mpifort CPP="cpp-14 -P  
-traditional"
```

And an editing of the file *make.inc* file was necessary in order to link properly the openblas library:

```
BLAS_LIBS      = -L/opt/homebrew/opt/openblas/lib -lopenblas  
LAPACK_LIBS = -L/opt/homebrew/opt/openblas/lib -lopenblas
```

Finally the compilation was done via the make command:

```
make pw pp
```

YAMBO branch tech-arm

The development necessary for the porting were committed in a dedicated branch, namely tech-arm¹³, of my fork of the official github YAMBO repository¹⁴:

In this branch, the following issues have been solved:

- The recognition of the operating system: *aarch64-apple-darwin23*
 - Solved adding few lines in *config/m4/acx_misc.m4*
- An issue related to openmp directives not supported by arm:

```
Undefined symbols for architecture arm64:  
  "_omp_destroy_lock_", referenced from:  
      ___openmp_MOD_openmp_locks_reset in  
libYmodules.a[6] (mod_openmp.o)  
[...]  
ld: symbol(s) not found for architecture arm64  
collect2: error: ld returned 1 exit status
```

- Solved adding **arm*apple** recognition in *config/m4/acx_fortran_flags.m4*

An additional issue was identified with the *mpicc* wrapper. It was expected to use the *gcc-14* C compiler internally; however, it was found to be using the *Apple Clang* compiler

¹³ <https://github.com/nicspalla/yambo/tree/tech-arm>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/yambo-code/yambo>

instead:

```
mpicc -show
clang -I/opt/homebrew/Cellar/open-mpi/5.0.5/include
      -L/opt/homebrew/Cellar/open-mpi/5.0.5/lib -lmpi
```

The issue was solved using the *OMPI_CC* environment variable to specify the C compiler:

```
export OMPI_CC=/opt/homebrew/bin/gcc-14
mpicc --show
/opt/homebrew/bin/gcc-14
      -I/opt/homebrew/Cellar/open-mpi/5.0.5/include
      -L/opt/homebrew/Cellar/open-mpi/5.0.5/lib -lmpi
```

Finally YAMBO has been successfully compiled with the following configuration:

```
export OMPI_CC=/opt/homebrew/bin/gcc-14
OPT=/opt/homebrew/opt

./configure \
  CC=gcc-14 \
  CPP="gcc-14 -E -P" \
  MPICC=mpicc \
  FC=gfortran-14 \
  F77=gfortran-14 \
  FPP="gfortran-14 -E -P" \
  MPIFC=mpifort \
  --enable-mpi \
  --enable-open-mp \
  --disable-hdf5-par-io \
  --enable-time-profile \
  --enable-memory-profile \
  --enable-msgs-comps \
  --with-blas-libs="-L$OPT/openblas/lib -lopenblas" \
  --with-lapack-libs="-L$OPT/openblas/lib -lopenblas" \
  --with-libxc-path=$OPT/libxc \
  --with-fft-path=$OPT/fftw \
  --with-hdf5-path=$OPT/hdf5 \
  --with-netcdf-path=$OPT/netcdf \
  --with-netcdf-f-path=$OPT/netcdf-fortran \
```

```
--enable-par-linalg \  
--with-scalapack-libs="-L$OPT/scalapack/lib -lscalapack" \  
--with-blacs-libs="-L$OPT/scalapack/lib -lscalapack" \  
--enable-slepc-linalg \  
--with-extlibs-path=$HOME/opt/ext-libs
```

```
make -j4 all
```

Porting on Fugaku

Fugaku is one of the world's most powerful supercomputers¹⁵, developed by RIKEN and Fujitsu in Japan, designed to tackle complex scientific, medical, and engineering challenges without exceptional processing speed and energy efficiency.

*System description*¹⁶:

- 158,976 nodes
 - two I/O network connections per rack
 - 3-level hierarchical storage system
- CPU A64FX
 - Architecture Armv8.2-A SVE (512 bit SIMD)
 - 48 cores for compute and 2/4 for OS activities
 - Normal: 2.0 GHz; Boost: 2.2 GHz
- OS Red Hat Enterprise Linux 8
 - McKernel (provided by RIKEN)
- Fujitsu MPI (based on Open MPI), RIKEN MPI (based on MPICH)
- LLIO (provided by Fujitsu)
- Application-oriented file IO libraries (provided by RIKEN)

COMPILATION IN INTERACTIVE MODE WITH SPACK

The development was continued, committing the needed modifications to the same branch tech-arm used in the previous section.

¹⁵ <https://top500.org/system/179807/>

¹⁶ <https://www.fujitsu.com/global/about/innovation/fugaku/specifications/>

- First of all it was added the support for platform *aarch64-unknown-linux-gnu* in *config/m4/acx_misc.m4* and *config/m4/acx_fortran_flags.m4*
- In order to compile code per the ARM nodes, it is necessary to launch the `pjsub` command, obtaining access to a compute node for the compilation in interactive mode:

```
pjsub --interact -g [group_id] -L "node=1" -L "rscgrp=int" -L
"elapse=6:00:00" --sparam "wait-time=600" --no-check-directory
```

- For facilitating the installation of all the dependencies, it was deployed of a private instance of the Spack¹⁷ package manager for Fugaku following this guide: https://www.fugaku.r-ccs.riken.jp/doc_root/en/user_guides/FugakuSpackGuide/intro.html#using-private-instance
- Before running the installation command of Spack, it was necessary to solve some issues related to the Fujitsu-MPI Spack recipe that exposes the wrong MPI wrappers when using the GCC compilers.
 - It was not possible to edit the Fujitsu-MPI recipe directly due to write protection, so modifications were applied to the library recipes for hdf5, netcdf and petsc
- For the same reason, an adjustment was also necessary for the YAMBO spack recipe¹⁸.
- An additional issue arose during the compilation of the SLEPc library. The SLEPc configure search for the MPI wrapper rather than using the command line argument, making it necessary to load the fujitsu-mpi package via Spack, before launching the “spack install” command.

YAMBO COMPILATION ON FUGAKU WITH SPACK

Once again having access to an ARM compute node in interactive mode, these commands were launched and the compilation of YAMBO succeeded. The compilation suite chosen for the installation was the GCC version 12.2.0 and the Fujitsu-MPI wrappers.

```
. ~/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
spack load fujitsu-mpi%gcc@12.2.0
spack install yambo@develop-arm %gcc@12.2.0
```

¹⁷ <https://spack.io/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/nicspalla/my-repo/commit/a850390d39c9211a6d39544ba8254875192d571d>

```
+mpi+openmp+memory+time+scalapack+slepc+nl+ph+sc+rt  
^fujitsu-mpi%gcc@12.2.0 ^libxc@5.2.3%gcc@12.2.0  
^openblas%gcc@12.2.0 ^netlib-scalapack%gcc@12.2.0
```

LAUNCHING THE GrCo GW WORKFLOW VIA BATCH SCRIPTS

YAMBO was successfully tested launching the [GrCo GW workflow](#) via batch scripts, starting from the ground state calculations with QUANTUM ESPRESSO.

- SCF and NSCF:

```
#!/bin/sh  
#PJM -S  
#PJM -L node=4  
#PJM --mpi max-proc-per-node=4  
#PJM -L rscgrp=small  
#PJM -L elapse=1:00:00  
#PJM -N grco_pw  
#PJM -g [group_id]  
#PJM -x PJM_LLIO_GFSCACHE=/vol0004  
  
. /vol0004/apps/oss/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh  
spack load quantum-espresso@7.3  
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/lib64:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH  
  
export PARALLEL=12  
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${PARALLEL}  
  
KPG=6 ; KPT=7 ; NSCFBANDS=2000  
cp scf.in scf_${KPT}k.in  
cp nscf.in nscf_${KPT}k.in  
for n in KPT KPG NSCFBANDS ; do  
    sed -i -e "s/${n}/${!n}/g" scf_${KPT}k.in  
    sed -i -e "s/${n}/${!n}/g" nscf_${KPT}k.in  
done  
  
mpiexec pw.x -npool 2 -input scf_${KPT}k.in >  
scf_${KPT}k.out_job-${PJM_JOBID}
```

```
mpiexec pw.x -npool 2 -input nscf_${KPT}k.in >
nscf_${KPT}k.out_job-${PJM_JOBID}
```

- **P2Y and YAMBO db initialization:**

```
#!/bin/sh
#PJM -S
#PJM -L node=1
#PJM --mpi max-proc-per-node=4
#PJM -L rscgrp=small
#PJM -L elapse=1:00:00
#PJM -N grco_p2y
#PJM -g [group_id]
#PJM -x PJM_LLIO_GFSCACHE=/vol0004

. ~/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
spack load yambo@develop-arm
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/lib64:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH

export PARALLEL=12
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${PARALLEL}
KPT=7
cd out_4l_${KPT}k/grco.save
mpiexec p2y
mpiexec yambo
cd ../..
```

- **YAMBO GW calculation:**

```
#!/bin/sh
#PJM -S
#PJM -L node=64
#PJM --mpi max-proc-per-node=4
#PJM -L rscgrp=small
#PJM -L elapse=2:00:00
#PJM -N grco_yambo
#PJM -g [group_id]
#PJM -x PJM_LLIO_GFSCACHE=/vol0004

. ~/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
```

```

spack load yambo@develop-arm
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/lib64:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH

export PARALLEL=12
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${PARALLEL}

# YAMBO
# MPI parallelization: processes distribution
# DIP_CPU= "K C V" # Dipoles driver
NDK=1 ; NDV=1 ; NDC=$((PJM_MPI_PROC/NDK/NDV))
# X_and_IO_CPU= "Q G K C V" # Response driver
NXQ=1 ; NXG=1 ; N XK=1 ; NXV=1 ; NXC=$((PJM_MPI_PROC/NDK/NDV))
# SE_CPU= "Q QP B" # Self Energy driver
NSQ=2 ; NSP=4 ; NSB=$((PJM_MPI_PROC/NSQ/NSP))

KPT=7 ; XNBANDS=2000 ; XCUTOFF=20

F_LABEL=grco_small_${PJM_MPI_PROC}mpi
J_SUFF=${OMP_NUM_THREADS}thrs_job-${PJM_JOBID}

cp ./yambo_grco.in ./yambo_${F_LABEL}.in
for n in NXQ NXG N XK NXC NXV NDK NDC NDV NSQ NSP NSB XNBANDS XCUTOFF
KPT ; do
    sed -i -e "s/${n}/${!n}/g" ./yambo_${F_LABEL}.in
done

mpiexec yambo -F yambo_${F_LABEL}.in \
    -J OUT_${F_LABEL}_${J_SUFF}.out \
    -C OUT_${F_LABEL}_${J_SUFF}.out

```

Porting on Deucalion

The Deucalion supercomputer has a heterogeneous architecture and is the first in Europe to incorporate ARM and x86 microprocessors in the same cluster.

System description¹⁹:

- 2,165 compute nodes
 - 1632 nodes ARM, CPU Fujitsu A64FX 48-core 2.0 GHz, no GPU
 - 500 nodes x86, CPU 2x AMD EPYC 7742 64-core 2.25 GHz, no GPU
 - 17 nodes x86, CPU 2x AMD EPYC 7742 64-core 2.25 GHz, GPU 4x NVIDIA Ampere A100 40 GB
 - 16 nodes x86, CPU 2x AMD EPYC 7742 64-core 2.25 GHz, GPU 4x NVIDIA Ampere A100 80 GB
- Operating System Rocky Linux 8
- Network NVIDIA Mellanox QM8790 with NVIDIA MLNX-OS

YAMBO COMPILATION ON DEUCALION IN INTERACTIVE MODE

The porting of the YAMBO code to Fugaku has allowed for its compilation on Deucalion as well, which, in the ARM partition, uses the same chip as Fugaku, without any further modifications to the source code. The chosen compilation suite for the installation is GCC v13.3.0 and OpenMPI v5.0.3.

- On Deucalion as well, it is necessary to compile interactively on an ARM node. For this reason, the user guide suggests using the following Slurm command and then logging into the compute node via SSH:

```
salloc -N1 -p dev-arm -t 4:00:00 -A [account_name]
ssh cna[xxxx]
```

- The same *tech-arm* branch used on Fugaku was also cloned on Deucalion and used for the compilation. Here these are the modules loaded before the configuration and the compilation via the *make* command:

```
module load gompi/2024a
module load ScaLAPACK/2.2.0-gompi-2024a-fb
module load HDF5/1.14.3-gompi-2024a
module load FFTW.MPI/3.3.10-gompi-2024a

./configure \
  CC=gcc \
```

¹⁹ <https://docs.macc.fcn.pt/deucalion/>

```

CPP="gcc -E -P" \
MPICC=mpicc \
FC=gfortran \
F77=gfortran \
FPP="gfortran -E -P" \
MPIFC=mpifort \
MPIF77=mpifort \
--enable-mpi \
--enable-open-mp \
--enable-hdf5-par-io \
--enable-time-profile \
--enable-memory-profile \
--enable-msgs-comps \
--with-blas-libs=$EBROOTOPENBLAS/lib/libopenblas.so \
--with-lapack-libs=$EBROOTOPENBLAS/lib/libopenblas.so \
--with-fft-path=$EBROOTFFTWMPI \
--with-hdf5-path=$EBROOTHDF5 \
--enable-slepc-linalg --enable-par-linalg \
--with-blacs-libs=$EBROOTSCALAPACK/lib/libscalapack.so \
--with-scalapack-libs=$EBROOTSCALAPACK/lib/libscalapack.so \
--with-extlibs-path=[specify a path in your project area]

make -j all

```

LAUNCHING THE GrCo GW WORKFLOW VIA BATCH SCRIPTS

YAMBO was successfully tested launching the [GrCo GW workflow](#) via batch scripts, starting from the ground state calculations with QUANTUM ESPRESSO. Here are reported only the last steps using YAMBO executables.

- P2Y and YAMBO db initialization:

```

#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --nodes=4
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=4
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=12
#SBATCH --partition=normal-arm
#SBATCH --time=01:00:00

```

```

#SBATCH --account=eehpc-dev-2024d10-121a
#SBATCH --mem=30000MB
#SBATCH --job-name=GrCo
#SBATCH --error=err.job-%j
#SBATCH --output=out.job-%j
#SBATCH --mail-type=ALL
#SBATCH --mail-user=nicola.spallanzani@nano.cnr.it

source /share/env/module_select.sh
module load gomp/2024a
module load ScaLAPACK/2.2.0-gomp/2024a-fb
module load HDF5/1.14.3-gomp/2024a
module load FFTW.MPI/3.3.10-gomp/2024a
export
PATH=/projects/EEHPC-DEV-2024D10-121/nspallan/src/yambo/bin:$PATH
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${SLURM_CPUS_PER_TASK}

KPT=7
cd out_41_${KPT}k/grco.save
mpirun -np 16 p2y
mpirun -np 16 yambo
cd ../..

```

- **YAMBO GW calculation:**

```

#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --nodes=64
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=4
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=12
#SBATCH --partition=normal-arm
#SBATCH --time=04:00:00
#SBATCH --account=eehpc-dev-2024d10-121a
#SBATCH --mem=30000MB
#SBATCH --job-name=GrCo
#SBATCH --error=err.job-%j
#SBATCH --output=out.job-%j

#SBATCH --mail-type=ALL

```

```

#SBATCH --mail-user=nicola.spallanzani@nano.cnr.it

source /share/env/module_select.sh
module load gOMPI/2024a
module load ScaLAPACK/2.2.0-gOMPI-2024a-fb
module load HDF5/1.14.3-gOMPI-2024a
module load FFTW.MPI/3.3.10-gOMPI-2024a
export
PATH=/projects/EEHPC-DEV-2024D10-121/nspallan/src/yambo/bin:$PATH
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=${SLURM_CPUS_PER_TASK}

F_LABEL=grco_small_${SLURM_NTASKS}mpi
J_SUFF=${SLURM_CPUS_PER_TASK}thrs_job-${SLURM_JOBID}

# YAMBO
# MPI parallelization: processes distribution
# DIP_CPU= "K C V" # Dipoles driver
NDK=1 ; NDV=1 ; NDC=$((SLURM_NTASKS/NDK/NDV))
# X_and_IO_CPU= "Q G K C V" # Response driver
NXQ=1 ; NXG=1 ; NXK=1 ; NXV=1 ; NXC=$((SLURM_NTASKS/NXK/NXV))
# SE_CPU= "Q QP B" # Self Energy driver
NSQ=2 ; NSP=4 ; NSB=$((SLURM_NTASKS/NSQ/NSP))

KPT=7 ; XNBANDS=2000 ; XCUTOFF=20
cp yambo_grco.in yambo_${F_LABEL}.in
for n in NXQ NXG NXK NXC NXV NDK NDC NDV NSQ NSP NSB XNBANDS XCUTOFF
KPT ; do
    sed -i -e "s/${n}/${!n}/g" yambo_${F_LABEL}.in
done

mpirun -np ${SLURM_NTASKS} yambo -F yambo_${F_LABEL}.in \
    -J ${F_LABEL}_${J_SUFF}.out -C ${F_LABEL}_${J_SUFF}.out

```

Conclusions

In conclusion, the porting of the YAMBO code to ARM architectures has been a success, both on everyday systems like Apple MacBooks and, more importantly, on highly parallel

HPC systems such as Fugaku and Deucalion. The supported compiler suite for this port is currently GCC, and in an upcoming effort, support for the Fujitsu compiler suite will be added, which is expected to bring performance improvements. Given the success of this endeavor, the tech-arm branch will soon be merged (via a pull request) into the tech-master branch of the official YAMBO repository. Installation recipes for various systems will be added to the YAMBO wiki pages once the code modifications are part of an official release. A further development of this work will involve running scalability tests to assess the parallel efficiency of YAMBO on ARM systems, allowing for comparisons with other architectures.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the developers of the YAMBO code, with whom I had the opportunity to exchange valuable insights on the topics covered in this report. In particular, I extend my special thanks to Andrea Ferretti, Daniele Varsano (CNR-NANO), Davide Sangalli and Andrea Marini (ISM-CNR) for their generous support and guidance throughout the course of my work.

MaX "MAterials design at the eXascale" co-funded by the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and participating countries under grant agreement No. 101093374.

Appendix

Benchmark GrCo input files

- SCF calculation with QUANTUM ESPRESSO:

```
&CONTROL
  calculation = 'scf',
  restart_mode='from_scratch',
  prefix='grco',
  pseudo_dir = './pseudo'
  outdir = './out_4l_KPTk'
/
&SYSTEM
 ibrav=4,
  celldm(1)=4.5919
  celldm(3)=15.0
  nat=7
  ntyp=3,
  ecutwfc=75
  occupations='smearing',
  smearing='gaussian',
  degauss=0.010,
  nspin=2,
  starting_magnetization(1) = 1.5d0
/
&ELECTRONS
  electron_maxstep = 250,
  conv_thr = 1.0d-8
  mixing_mode = 'local-TF'
  mixing_beta = 0.3d0
/
&IONS
/
ATOMIC_SPECIES
Co  58.933    Co.upf
C   12.011    C.upf
```

```

H      1.008      H.upf
ATOMIC_POSITIONS (angstrom)
  H      1.2149639450    0.7014597470    1.2210789440
  Co     -0.0000000120    1.4029195150    2.1412486210
  Co      0.0000000000    0.0000000000    4.0913924790
  Co     -0.0000000120    1.4029195150    6.0466580170
  Co      0.0000000000    0.0000000000    7.9631843810
  C      0.0000000000    0.0000000000   10.0188391090
  C      1.2149639450    0.7014597470    9.9936362370
K_POINTS (automatic)
KPG KPG 1      0 0 0

```

- NSCF calculation with QUANTUM ESPRESSO:

```

&CONTROL
  calculation = 'nscf',
  restart_mode='from_scratch',
  prefix='grco',
  pseudo_dir = './pseudo'
  outdir = './out_41_KPTk'
/
&SYSTEM
 ibrav=4,
  celldm(1)=4.5919
  celldm(3)=15.0
  nat=7
  ntyp=3,
  ecutwfc=75
  occupations='smearing',
  smearing='gaussian',
  degauss=0.010,
  nspin=2,
  starting_magnetization(1) = 1.5d0
  nbnd=NSCFBANDS
/
&ELECTRONS
  electron_maxstep = 250,
  conv_thr = 1.0d-8

```

```

    mixing_mode = 'local-TF'
    mixing_beta = 0.3d0
/
&IONS
/
ATOMIC_SPECIES
Co  58.933    Co.upf
C   12.011    C.upf
H   1.008     H.upf
ATOMIC_POSITIONS (angstrom)
  H   1.2149639450    0.7014597470    1.2210789440
  Co  -0.0000000120    1.4029195150    2.1412486210
  Co   0.0000000000    0.0000000000    4.0913924790
  Co  -0.0000000120    1.4029195150    6.0466580170
  Co   0.0000000000    0.0000000000    7.9631843810
  C   0.0000000000    0.0000000000   10.0188391090
  C   1.2149639450    0.7014597470    9.9936362370
K_POINTS (automatic)
KPG KPG 1    0 0 0

```

- GW calculation with YAMBO

```

gw0          # [R] GW approximation
ppa # [R][Xp] Plasmon Pole Approximation for the Screened
        Interaction
rim_cut      # [R] Coulomb potential
HF_and_locXC # [R] Hartree-Fock
em1d        # [R][X] Dynamically Screened Interaction
NLogCPUs=   10 # [PARALLEL] Live-timing CPU`s (0 for all)
DIP_CPU=    "NDK NDC NDV" # [PARALLEL] CPUs for each role
DIP_ROLES=  "k c v"      # [PARALLEL] CPUs roles (k,c,v)
DIP_Threads= 0          # [OPENMP/X] Number of threads for dipoles
X_and_IO_CPU= "NXQ NXG NXK NXC NXV" # [PARALLEL] CPUs for each role
X_and_IO_ROLES= "q g k c v"      # [PARALLEL] CPUs roles (q,g,k,c,v)
X_and_IO_nCPU_LinAlg_INV= -1    # [PARALLEL] CPUs for Linear Algebra
        (if -1 it is automatically set)
X_Threads= 0          # [OPENMP/X] Number of threads for response functions
SE_CPU=    "NSQ NSP NSB" # [PARALLEL] CPUs for each role

```

```

SE_ROLEs= "q qp b"      # [PARALLEL] CPUs roles (q,qp,b)
SE_Threads= 0           # [OPENMP/GW] Number of threads for self-energy
RandQpts= 3000000       # [RIM] Number of random q-points in the BZ
RandGvec= 1   RL        # [RIM] Coulomb interaction RS components
CUTGeo= "box z"         # [CUT] Coulomb Cutoff geometry:
                        box/cylinder/sphere/ws/slab X/Y/Z/XY..
% CUTBox
  0.000000 | 0.000000 | 68.00000 |   # [CUT] [au] Box sides
%
CUTRadius= 0.000000     # [CUT] [au] Sphere/Cylinder radius
CUTCylLen= 0.000000     # [CUT] [au] Cylinder length
CUTwsGvec= 0.700000     # [CUT] WS cutoff: number of G to be modified
EXXRLvcs= 110539   RL   # [XX] Exchange      RL components
VXCRLvcs= 110539   RL   # [XC] XCpotential RL components
Chimod= "HARTREE"     # [X] IP/Hartree/ALDA/LRC/PF/BSfxc
% QpntsRXp
  1 | KPT |             # [Xp] Transferred momenta
%
% BndsRnXp
  1 | XNBANDS |         # [Xp] Polarization function bands
%
NGsBlkXp= XCUTOFF     Ry # [Xp] Response block size
% LongDrXp
  0.577350E-5 | 0.577350E-5 | 0.577350E-5 # [Xp] [cc] Electric Field
%
PPAPntXp= 1.000000    Ha # [Xp] PPA imaginary energy
% GbndRnge
  1 | XNBANDS |         # [GW] G[W] bands range
%
GTermKind= "none"     # [GW] GW terminator ("none","BG"
                        Bruneval-Gonze,"BRS" Berger-Reining-Sottile)
DysSolver= "n"        # [GW] Dyson Equation solver ("n","s","g")
%QPkrange             # [GW] QP generalized Kpoint/Band indices
  KPT| KPT| 35| 36|
  KPT| KPT| 40| 41|
  1| 1| 38| 39|
  1| 1| 44| 45|

```

